

Animal Model w/ random effects only: animModel_1M_thin5K_x6_sigma1

FINAL MODEL - No Fixed effects – USED IN MS

```
#Load model output
load(file="animModel_1M_thin5K_x6.RData")

### Summarize each run of model
summary(model_6chains[[1]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21656.23
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean  l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal    0.4559 9.021e-05   1.285   123.8
##
##      ~dam
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam    0.1402  0.02269  0.2241   120.5
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units         1         1         1         0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ 1
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept)  0.10902  0.04311  0.18383   180 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

effectiveSize(model_6chains[[1]]$Sol)

## (Intercept)
##          180

effectiveSize(model_6chains[[1]]$VCV)
```

```

## animal dam units
## 123.8232 120.4905 0.0000

summary(model_6chains[[2]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21659.94
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
## post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal 0.4282 0.01078 1.322 180
##
## ~dam
##
## post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam 0.1437 0.03123 0.2345 341.9
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
## post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units 1 1 1 0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ 1
##
## post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept) 0.10970 0.04051 0.18802 180 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[3]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21662.02
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
## post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal 0.4075 0.0002422 1.044 240.8
##
## ~dam
##
## post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp

```

```

## dam    0.1464  0.02335  0.2333    180
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units          1      1      1          0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ 1
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept)  0.10298  0.03281  0.16711    180 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[4]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21659.65
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean  l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal    0.3957 0.0002935  1.051    180
##
##      ~dam
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam    0.1467  0.04463  0.2559    180
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units          1      1      1          0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ 1
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept)  0.10537  0.04306  0.18520    180 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[5]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180

```

```

##
## DIC: 21671.67
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal    0.3966 0.000103    1.11    180
##
##      ~dam
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam      0.1459 0.01942 0.2293    180
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units          1      1      1      0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ 1
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept) 0.10702 0.04904 0.18186    180 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[6]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21653.48
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal    0.4129 0.001467    1.169    180
##
##      ~dam
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam      0.143 0.02734 0.2385    180
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units          1      1      1      0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ 1

```

```

##
##           post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp  pMCMC
## (Intercept)  0.10409  0.04605  0.17641      229 0.0111 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

### Summarize 6 chains
animCh1 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[1]]$VCV)
animCh2 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[2]]$VCV)
animCh3 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[3]]$VCV)
animCh4 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[4]]$VCV)
animCh5 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[5]]$VCV)
animCh6 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[6]]$VCV)

ES_VCV_Ch1 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[1]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch2 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[2]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch3 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[3]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch4 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[4]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch5 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[5]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch6 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[6]]$VCV)

library(dplyr)

##
## Attaching package: 'dplyr'

## The following objects are masked from 'package:stats':
##
##   filter, lag

## The following objects are masked from 'package:base':
##
##   intersect, setdiff, setequal, union

resultsVCV_UP_noFE <- bind_rows(animCh1, animCh2, animCh3, animCh4,animCh5,an
imCh6)
ES_VCV_UP_noFE <- bind_rows(ES_VCV_Ch1, ES_VCV_Ch2, ES_VCV_Ch3, ES_VCV_Ch4,ES
_VCV_Ch5,ES_VCV_Ch6)

SolCh1 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[1]]$Sol)
SolCh2 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[2]]$Sol)
SolCh3 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[3]]$Sol)
SolCh4 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[4]]$Sol)
SolCh5 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[5]]$Sol)
SolCh6 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[6]]$Sol)

ES_Sol_Ch1 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[1]]$Sol)
ES_Sol_Ch2 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[2]]$Sol)
ES_Sol_Ch3 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[3]]$Sol)
ES_Sol_Ch4 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[4]]$Sol)
ES_Sol_Ch5 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[5]]$Sol)

```

```
ES_Sol_Ch6 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[6])$Sol)

resultsSol_UP_noFE <- bind_rows(SolCh1, SolCh2, SolCh3, SolCh4,SolCh5,SolCh6)
ES_Sol_UP_noFE <- bind_rows(ES_Sol_Ch1, ES_Sol_Ch2, ES_Sol_Ch3, ES_Sol_Ch4,ES
_Sol_Ch5,ES_Sol_Ch6)

### BELOW USED TO CHECK MIXING OF CHAINS IN PARALLEL
animalChains_UP_noFE <- cbind(animCh1,animCh2,animCh3,animCh4,animCh5,animCh6
)
names(animalChains_UP_noFE) <- c("anim1","dam1","unit1","anim2","dam2","unit2
","anim3","dam3","unit3", "anim4","dam4","unit4", "anim5","dam5","unit5", "an
im6","dam6","unit6")
base <- ggplot(animalChains_UP_noFE, aes(x=as.numeric(row.names(animalChains_
UP_noFE)), y=anim1, group=3)) + geom_path()

base + geom_path(aes(x=as.numeric(row.names(animalChains_UP_noFE)), y=anim2,
group=1), colour="blue") + geom_path(aes(x=as.numeric(row.names(animalChains_
UP_noFE)), y=anim3, group=1), colour="green") + geom_path(aes(x=as.numeric(ro
w.names(animalChains_UP_noFE)), y=anim4, group=1), colour="red") + geom_path(
aes(x=as.numeric(row.names(animalChains_UP_noFE)), y=anim5, group=1), colour=
"orange") + geom_path(aes(x=as.numeric(row.names(animalChains_UP_noFE)), y=an
im6, group=1), colour="maroon1")
```



```
### Check autocorrs
autocorr(model_6chains[[1])$VCV)

## , , animal
##
```

```

##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      1.00000000 -0.86172886  NaN
## Lag 5000   0.18219278 -0.18723004  NaN
## Lag 25000 -0.01039311  0.04786532  NaN
## Lag 50000  0.14984441 -0.15405365  NaN
## Lag 250000 0.01535631 -0.01122227  NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      -0.86172886  1.00000000  NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.19506050  0.19534843  NaN
## Lag 25000  0.02695258 -0.07446354  NaN
## Lag 50000 -0.12859029  0.11656794  NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.00361460  0.03913453  NaN
##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 25000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 50000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 250000 NaN NaN  NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[2]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      1.000000000 -0.826934998  NaN
## Lag 5000   0.004520054  0.093745016  NaN
## Lag 25000  0.009722898 -0.061873364  NaN
## Lag 50000  0.039992631  0.005879773  NaN
## Lag 250000 0.086656553 -0.057461197  NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      -0.82693500  1.00000000  NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.01304942 -0.09572632  NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.02045069  0.02548903  NaN
## Lag 50000  -0.08967382  0.02055992  NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.08868719  0.07140746  NaN
##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN  NaN

```

Removing chain 1 from summaries did not change overall estimates of h2 and 95% CI.

```
## Lag 25000      NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 50000      NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 250000     NaN NaN   NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[3]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      1.00000000 -0.76627518   NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.14714467  0.08925380   NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.06439240  0.02596272   NaN
## Lag 50000  -0.05990500  0.10818341   NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.01056151  0.02432541   NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      -0.76627518  1.00000000   NaN
## Lag 5000    0.14127960 -0.05995717   NaN
## Lag 25000   0.06362090 -0.04140149   NaN
## Lag 50000   0.03119814 -0.04187107   NaN
## Lag 250000  0.01874672 -0.02748416   NaN
##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 5000    NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 25000   NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 50000   NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 250000  NaN NaN   NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[4]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      1.00000000 -0.85259754   NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.07846560  0.06321897   NaN
## Lag 25000  0.08433969 -0.05793865   NaN
## Lag 50000  0.06127490 -0.04603863   NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.09489293  0.11193542   NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      -0.85259754  1.00000000   NaN
## Lag 5000    0.05198093 -0.05418162   NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.07964145  0.08978455   NaN
## Lag 50000  -0.07189776  0.05992490   NaN
```

```
## Lag 250000 0.13094978 -0.12780167 NaN
##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 25000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 50000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 250000 NaN NaN  NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[5]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##          animal      dam units
## Lag 0      1.00000000 -0.82349270 NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.07679051 0.06857891 NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.02288910 0.02617018 NaN
## Lag 50000  -0.07966987 0.13163930 NaN
## Lag 250000 0.03923116 -0.09021233 NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##          animal      dam units
## Lag 0      -0.82349270 1.00000000 NaN
## Lag 5000    0.01943932 -0.02889453 NaN
## Lag 25000   0.05425574 -0.08931010 NaN
## Lag 50000   0.03519465 -0.08984330 NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.03220306 0.06395636 NaN
##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 25000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 50000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 250000 NaN NaN  NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[6]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##          animal      dam units
## Lag 0      1.00000000 -0.82366123 NaN
## Lag 5000    0.009895664 -0.05121654 NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.050763310 0.04599781 NaN
## Lag 50000  0.036217611 -0.04251250 NaN
## Lag 250000 0.085907521 -0.02060319 NaN
##
```

```

## , , dam
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      -0.823661227  1.000000000  NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.029641042  0.032926903  NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.010142376  0.005150497  NaN
## Lag 50000  -0.007422375  -0.001459735  NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.074809997  0.023738286  NaN
##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 25000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 50000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 250000 NaN NaN  NaN

require(QGglmm)
n <- length(resultsSol_UP_noFE$`(Intercept)`)
mu <- mean(resultsSol_UP_noFE$`(Intercept)`)
va <- mean(resultsVCV_UP_noFE$animal)
vd <- mean(resultsVCV_UP_noFE$dam)
vp <- mean(rowSums(resultsVCV_UP_noFE)-1)

QGparams(mu=mu, var.a=va, var.p=vp, model= "binom1.probit", closed.form = FALSE)

## [1] "Computing observed mean..."
## [1] "Computing variances..."
## [1] "Computing Psi..."

##   mean.obs  var.obs  var.a.obs   h2.obs
## 1 0.5339271 0.248849 0.04213612 0.1693241

QGicc(mu=mu, var.comp= vd, var.p=vp, model= "binom1.probit")

## [1] "Using a semi-closed form for a binom1.probit model."

## Warning in QGicc(mu = mu, var.comp = vd, var.p = vp, model = "binom1.probit"): Some component (var.comp.obs) are not totally
##   from a closed form solution: an integral is computed

##   mean.obs  var.obs  var.comp.obs   icc.obs
## 1 0.5339271 0.248849 0.01463748 0.05882073

QGicc(mu=mu, var.comp=va+vd, var.p=vp, model="binom1.probit")

## [1] "Using a semi-closed form for a binom1.probit model."

```

```
## Warning in QGicc(mu = mu, var.comp = va + vd, var.p = vp, model = "binom1.
probit"): Some component (var.comp.obs) are not totally
##           from a closed form solution: an integral is computed

##   mean.obs  var.obs var.comp.obs  icc.obs
## 1 0.5339271 0.248849  0.05810676 0.2335021

## Heritability on Liability scale
herit_liab_UP_noFE <- resultsVCV_UP_noFE$animal / rowSums(resultsVCV_UP_noFE)
mean(herit_liab_UP_noFE)

## [1] 0.236541

HPDinterval(as.mcmc(herit_liab_UP_noFE))

##           lower      upper
## var1 7.282941e-05 0.5149511
## attr(,"Probability")
## [1] 0.95

#### Below is from deVillemereuil2021 (zotero) - tutorial 2, Section 4.2, p.
37

### Heritability on Observed scale
## pmap_dfr is a purr function that works similarly to mapply
library(purrr)
paramsB_UP_noFE <-
  pmap_dfr(list(mu = resultsSol_UP_noFE$(Intercept),
               var.a = resultsVCV_UP_noFE$animal,
               var.p = rowSums(resultsVCV_UP_noFE)-1), ## See de Villemereu
            il 2021 p. 37 for explanation of -1
            QGparams,
            model = "binom1.probit",
            verbose = FALSE)
mean(paramsB_UP_noFE[["h2.obs"]])

## [1] 0.1501135

HPDinterval(as.mcmc(paramsB_UP_noFE[["h2.obs"]]))

##           lower      upper
## var1 4.627768e-05 0.3271685
## attr(,"Probability")
## [1] 0.95

plot(as.mcmc(resultsVCV_UP_noFE$animal))
```



```
heidel.diag(as.mcmc(resultsVCV_UP_noFE))  
  
##  
##      Stationarity start      p-value  
##      test      iteration  
## animal passed          1      0.253  
## dam   passed          1      0.475  
## units failed          NA          NA  
##  
##      Halfwidth Mean  Halfwidth  
##      test  
## animal passed    0.416 0.0224  
## dam   passed    0.144 0.0031  
## units <NA>      NA      NA  
  
library(coda)  
library(lattice)  
densityplot(as.mcmc(paramsB_UP_noFE[["h2.obs"]]))
```



```

library(ggplot2)
#h2_IP <- as.data.frame(as.mcmc(paramsB_IP[["h2.obs"]]))
h2_UP_noFE <- as.data.frame(as.mcmc(paramsB_UP_noFE[["h2.obs"]]))

#HPD_plot <- ggplot(data=h2_IP) + geom_density(aes(x=var1, colour="var1"), show.legend=FALSE) + geom_rug(aes(x=var1, colour="var1"), show.legend = FALSE) + labs(x="Heritabililty", y="Density") + xlim(0,0.5) + theme_classic() + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = rel(2)), axis.title.x = element_text(size=rel(2.5)), axis.title.y = element_text(size=rel(2.5)), axis.line.x.bottom = element_line(size=1), axis.line.y.left = element_line(size=1)) + geom_density(data=h2, aes(x=var1)) + geom_rug(data=h2, aes(x=var1)) + theme(panel.background = element_rect(fill = "transparent", colour = NA), plot.background = element_rect(fill = "transparent", colour = NA))

### FROM: https://github.com/devillemereuil/prior-MCMCglmm/blob/master/priors.R

library(mvtnorm)
library(MCMCglmm)
library(ggplot2)
library(progress)

## ----- Prior model for monovariate

## Parameters
K <- 1e+05 # Number of iterations
nu <- 1000 # nu parameter = 1000 for default prior

```

```

alpha.mu <- 0 # alpha.mu parameter = 0 for default prior
alpha.V <- 1 # alpha.V parameter = 1 for default prior

### my initial informed prior was nu=1000, alpha.mu=0.6, alpha.V=0.05 IP2 is
### nu=5, alpha.mu=0.7, alpha.V=0.05

## Prior for extended parameter Va Variance of eta
pr_var_eta <- rIW(n = K, V = diag(1), nu = nu)[, 1]
# Alpha
pr_alpha <- rnorm(K, alpha.mu, sqrt(alpha.V))
# Resulting prior on Va
pr_var_a <- (pr_alpha^2) * pr_var_eta

## Prior for residual variance Essentially useless for a binary trait, as fix
=
## 1... but keeping it in case we want to remove fix = 1
pr_var_r <- rIW(n = K, V = diag(1), nu = 1, fix = 1)[, 1]

## Resulting prior for heritability
pr_herit_Chi1 <- pr_var_a/(pr_var_a + pr_var_r)

## Plotting the density of the prior qplot(x = pr_heritIP2, geom = 'density')
## prior_plot <- ggplot() + geom_density(aes(x=pr_herit_Chi1)) +
## geom_density(aes(x=pr_heritIP2, colour='red'), show.legend = FALSE) +
## labs(title = 'Prior Distributions', x='Prob. Heritabililty', y='Density')
+
## xlim(0,1) + theme_classic() + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = rel(2)
),
## axis.title.x = element_text(size= rel(2.5)), axis.title.y =
## element_text(size=rel(2.5)), axis.line.x.bottom = element_line(size=1),
## axis.line.y.left = element_line(size=1), panel.background =
## element_rect(fill = 'transparent', colour = NA), plot.background =
## element_rect(fill = 'transparent', colour = NA)) prior_plot library(ggpubr
)
## figure <- ggarrange(prior_plot, HPD_plot, ncol=1, nrow=2) figure
## ggsave('priors3.tiff', figure,width=8,height=8, bg='transparent')

```